

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to Dr. S. P. Banerjee, Professor and Head, Department of Chemistry, for facilities.

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Chemical Studies on some $\text{Ni}(\text{amine})_n^+ \text{MoO}_4^{2-}$ Complexes

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Manuscript received 30 September 1986, revised 28 July 1987, accepted 22 August 1987

In our previous paper, we communicated some structural aspects of amine complexes of Ni^{II} having WO_4^{2-} as anion¹. In this communication, we report the preparation and characterisation of some complexes of Ni^{II} with various amines having MoO_4^{2-} as anion. The complexes have been characterised on the basis of elemental analysis, molar conductance, magnetic, infrared, electronic spectra and X-ray powder diffraction data. The aim of investigation is to study the coordination behaviour of Ni^{II} in presence of a different anion.

Experimental

The starting material nickel molybdate was prepared by the reported method². The complexes were isolated by shaking nickel molybdate (0.01 mol) with the required amine (0.03 mol) in ethanol (~100 ml). The contents were shaken for ~12 h. The complexation was marked by change in colour from light yellow to violet/purple/pink. The products were filtered washed 3-4 times with ethanol. The complexes were dissolved in distilled water and recrystallised, and washed with ethanol and dried in vacuum over P_4O_{10} before analysis.

Nickel and molybdenum in the complexes were determined gravimetrically as bis-glyoximate nickel(II) and lead molybdate, respectively³. Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen were analysed at C.D.R.I., Lucknow. Ir spectra (CsI) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 397 spectrophotometer. The room temperature magnetic moments of the complexes were determined by Gouy method using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_4]$ as standard. All other chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. The X-ray powder pattern was recorded on a diffractometer using CuK_α ($\lambda=1.5418 \text{ \AA}$) radiation at I.I.T., Bombay. The diffractogram was obtained at scanning speed of $1^\circ (2\theta) \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and chart speed 2 cm min^{-1} .

Results and Discussion

Table 1 reports the analytical, magnetic and conductance data. From elemental analyses the molecular formulae of complexes work out to be $\text{NiL}_3\text{MoO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ for $\text{L}=\text{en}$, $\text{NiL}_3\text{MoO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ for $\text{L}=\text{Pn}$, and $\text{NiL}_3\text{MoO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ for $\text{L}=\text{dien}$. The magnetic moment values of the complexes lie in the range 2.99-3.18 B.M., which are in good agreement with the reported values of Ni^{II} complexes in octahedral field (2.92-3.41 B.M.) corresponding to two unpaired electrons^{4,5}. The molar conductance values ($227-247 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) indicate the ionic nature of the complexes⁶.

The electronic spectra of the complexes show three prominent bands at 13 106-13 172 (ν_1), 18 488-18 867 (ν_2) and 30 556-29 872 (ν_3) which correspond to the transitions ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g} (F)$, ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g} (F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g} (P)$, respectively. The band positions suggest the octahedral geometry of the six-coordinate complexes^{7,8}. The B values vary from 637 to 668 cm^{-1} . The Racah parameter have been found to be 60% for $\text{Ni}(\text{dien})_3\text{MoO}_4$, 63% for $\text{Ni}(\text{en})_3\text{MoO}_4$ and 68% for $\text{Ni}(\text{Pn})_3\text{MoO}_4$ of the free ion value (1 080 cm^{-1})⁹. This could be due to distortion of the O_h symmetry in aqueous solution of the complexes.

The comparison of the ir spectra of pure ligands and those of complexes has been made. The assignments of ir spectra have been given on the basis of reported ir data of the amine complexes^{10,11}. A negative shift in N-H stretching have been noted in all the complexes. The N-H vibrations in various complexes appear as follows: $\text{Ni}(\text{en})_3\text{MoO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ 3 260m, 3 220m and 3 110m (in free ligand 3 305, 3 290); $\text{Ni}(\text{Pn})_3\text{MoO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ 3 250m and 3 120s on the lower energy side than the free ligands (3 260s and 3 320s); diethylenetriamine 3 340s, 3 250s and 3 160m but in the complex these bands appears at 3 320s, 3 179s, 3 119s. All complexes show a broad band around 3 500 cm^{-1} and weak band around 1 600 cm^{-1} indicating the presence of water of crystallisation^{12,13}. The ir band due to oxo anion MoO_4^{2-} in these complexes were identified as follows. In the complexes $\text{Ni}(\text{en})_3\text{MoO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Ni}(\text{Pn})_3\text{MoO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Ni}(\text{dien})_3\text{MoO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, the ν_1 , ν_2 and ν_3 appear at

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF Ni^{II}(amine)_nMoO₄ COMPLEXES

Compd	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			Λ _M Ω ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹	μ _{eff} [*] B.M.
		Ni	N	Mo		
Ni(en) ₂ MoO ₄ ·2H ₂ O	Violet	18.47 (18.58)	18.88 (19.81)	22.06 (22.01)	286	3.18
Ni(Pn) ₂ MoO ₄ ·H ₂ O	Purple	15.06 (15.24)	18.64 (18.8)	20.91 (21.00)	227	3.13
Ni(dien) ₂ MoO ₄ ·H ₂ O	Pink	13.23 (13.5)	18.89 (18.97)	21.68 (21.50)	247	2.99

* At 298 K.

897vw, 310vs and 842vw cm⁻¹, 890s, 315s and 837vw cm⁻¹ and 915s, 310s and 840vw cm⁻¹, respectively. The N–M stretching band for all complexes^{1,4} lie in the range 500–550 cm⁻¹. The negative shift in the amine absorptions indicates the coordination through N atom of the ligand^{1,5}.

The octahedral complexes showed characteristic X-ray powder diffraction pattern (Table 2). The unit cell for tris(1,2-diaminopropane)nickel(II)-molybdate and tris(1,2-diaminoethane)nickel(II)

The data reveal that the most frequently occurring ratio is 3 for some values of sin²θ which is characteristic of hexagonal system. The calculated values are in good agreement with the experimental values. The X-ray work on Ni₁(dien)₂MoO₄·H₂O is in progress.

When compared with complexes containing WO₄²⁻ it is found that both have similar octahedral geometry, but WO₄²⁻ complexes show much distortion. The unit cells of MoO₄²⁻ complexes are found to have hexagonal symmetry while Ni(en)₂WO₄ and Ni(Pn)₂WO₄ are cubic and tetragonal, respectively.

TABLE 2—X-RAY DATA OF Ni^{II}(amine)_nMoO₄ COMPLEXES

Peak no.	2θ	Relative intensity I/I ₀ × 100	(hkl)	Calculated sin ² θ	Observed sin ² θ
(I) Ni ^{II} (1,2-diaminoethane)MoO ₄					
1.	10.4	85.35	(100)	0.008 21	0.008 21
2.	17.9	100.00	(110)	0.024 6	0.024 1
3.	20.7	56.68	(200)	0.032 8	0.032 2
4.	22.6	50.95	(201)	0.038 8	0.038 3
5.	25.4	60.50	(112)	0.048 8	0.048 3
6.	27.6	25.79	(310)	0.057 4	0.056 8
7.	28.9	17.19	(103)	0.062 7	0.062 2
8.	31.3	10.19	(300)	0.073 8	0.075 0
9.	33.0	29.29	(301)	0.079 9	0.080 6
10.	36.3	28.66	(220)	0.098 5	0.097 0
11.	40.7	24.20	(222)	0.122 5	0.120 8
12.	45.9	12.10	(223)	0.152 9	0.152 0
(II) Ni ^{II} (1,2-diaminopropane) ₂ MoO ₄					
1.	11.1	62.99	(100)	0.009 35	0.009 35
2.	17.8	100.00	(002)	0.028 9	0.028 9
3.	19.3	40.15	(110)	0.028 0	0.028 0
4.	21.1	14.96	(102)	0.032 2	0.032 5
5.	22.3	21.25	(200)	0.037 4	0.037 3
6.	24.0	25.11	(201)	0.043 3	0.043 2
7.	26.4	31.49	(112)	0.051 93	0.052 1
8.	32.7	31.14	(113)	0.081	0.079 2
9.	38.4	7.08	(302)	0.108 0	0.107 6
	A	C	a	c	
For (I)	0.008 21	0.006 0547	9.824 169 Å	9.907 2 Å	
For (II)	0.009 35	0.005 983	9.205 801 4 Å	9.966 412 3 Å	

molybdate has been found to be hexagonal type with lattice constants: a = b = 9.824 169 Å, C = 9.907 2 Å and a = b = 9.205 8 Å, C = 9.966 412 3 Å, respectively. The cell parameters have been calculated using the equation^{1,6},

$$\sin^2\theta(hkl) = (\lambda^2/3a^2)(h^2 + hk + K^2) + (\lambda^2/4C^2)l^2$$

or

$$\sin^2\theta(hkl) = A(h^2 + hk + K^2) + Cl^2$$

Acknowledgement

The authors thank C.D.R.I., Lucknow, for elemental analysis and infrared studies. The authors also thank Mr. A. B. Khare, Department of Chemistry, Dr. Harisingh Gour Vishwavidyalaya, Sagar, for helpful discussion.

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